

How sense-making drives successful partnerships

Two case studies

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Partnerships in online learning are becoming increasingly common in higher education. Third space professionals (Whitchurch, 2012), such as learning designers, often play a critical role in these partnerships by setting standards, developing processes and building relationships. They often act as brokers and border-crossers (Keppell, 2007), working across various stakeholder groups to help enhance course quality and student learning (Abblitt, 2024), as well as to influence change and innovation at the interpersonal, professional, institutional, and societal levels (D’Souza et al., 2022). Key to success in these partnerships is sense-making, which helps foster empathy, collaboration, innovation, and resilience by focusing on people rather than process alone.

We share two case studies of third space professional experiences with sensemaking to drive successful partnership outcomes.

- The first case relates to high-level onboarding and maintenance of partnerships, involving a range of stakeholders from client services to faculty.
- The second relates to nurturing effective course co-design relationships between academics and learning designers.

We hope participants in the session gained insights into the role of “third space” professionals in sensemaking and relationship building in fulfilling educational partnerships, so that less time can be spent on resolving challenges and more on collaborating to create an excellent student experience.

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